

Breast Cancer Now	
Data management plan required?	Encouraged, but not reviewed as part of the funding decision
RDM policy Link	No link
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	Data quality, standards and metadata (utilising acceptable community standards and allowing data to be easily discovered), methods for data sharing and how to access data (deposition in existing public databases or via third party request). Potential for secondary reuse and how new data links to old data. Timeframes for public release
Required data repository	Not specified
Time for data release	Not specified
Time for long-term storage of data	Not specified
Costings	Not specified
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	grants_admin@breastcancer.org
Comments	Member of the National Cancer Research Institution and has contributed to the NCRI Informatics Initiative

Documents used:

Breast cancer now - Project grant guidelines.

<https://breastcancer.org/sites/default/files/public/project-grant-guidelines-nov-2018.pdf>

(Updated version)

Accessed: May 2018